

**Contributions to the taxonomy and biogeography of Campopleginae:
new species, new combination, new synonymies, and new records
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)**

Zoltán Vas

*Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum,
Department of Zoology, Hymenoptera Collection, H-1088 Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary.*

E-mail: vas.zoltan@nhmus.hu

Abstract – Taxonomical and biogeographical results on Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from the Palaearctic, Oriental, Australasian and Neotropical regions are presented. *Casinaria molnari* sp. nov. is described from Brazil, *Hyposoter jolanae* sp. nov. from Paraguay. New subjective synonymies proposed: *Breviterebra laticlypeata* Kusigemati, 1982 = *Breviterebra apicocrinis* Han, van Achterberg et Chen, 2022, syn. nov.; *Melalophacharops tamanukii* Uchida, 1928 = *Microcharops ussuriensis* Kasparyan, 1985, syn. nov.; *Limnerium bombycivorum* Cameron, 1911 = *Eriborus biroi* Vas, 2023, syn. nov.; problems in the generic diagnoses and identification of *Eriborus* Förster, 1869 and *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869 in the Australasian and Oriental regions are highlighted. New combination proposed: *Melalophacharops australis* (Kusigemati, 1981), comb. nov., transferred from *Microcharops* Roman, 1910. New country records: *Campoplex rufocingulatus* Horstmann et Yu, 1999, *Dusona bicoloripes* (Ashmead, 1906), and *Hyposoter virginalis* (Gravenhorst, 1829) for Hungary, *Enytus apostatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829) for North Macedonia and Algeria, *Hyposoter caedator* (Gravenhorst, 1829) for Bosnia and Herzegovina, and *Tranosema latiusculum* Thomson, 1887 for China, the latter representing the first report of the species from the Eastern Palaearctic Region.

Key words – species description, synonymy, distribution, Gábor Molnár, *Breviterebra*, *Campoplex*, *Casinaria*, *Dusona*, *Hyposoter*, *Enytus*, *Eriborus*, *Melalophacharops*, *Microcharops*, *Tranosema*

INTRODUCTION

Recent results of the ongoing taxonomical and biogeographical work on Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) in the Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM) are presented in this paper, concerning the genera *Breviterebra* Kusigemati, 1982, *Campoplex* Gravenhorst, 1829, *Casinaria* Holmgren, 1859, *Dusona* Cameron, 1901, *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869, *Enytus*

Cameron, 1905, *Eriborus* Förster, 1869, *Melalophacharops* Uchida, 1928, *Microcharops* Roman, 1910, and *Tranosema* Förster, 1869. Two new species are described from the Neotropical Region (Brazil and Paraguay), three new subjective synonymies and a new combination are proposed, and new country records are presented for six species. Problems in the generic diagnoses and identification of *Eriborus* Förster, 1869 and *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869 in the Australasian and Oriental regions are highlighted.

Taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU & HORSTMANN (1997) and YU *et al.* (2016). Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997); however, for wing venation the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also used. Terminology of body surface sculpturing follows HARRIS (1979). Identifications were based on the works of SAY (1835), CRESSON (1865, 1872, 1874), SCHROTTKY (1902), TOSQUINET (1903), CAMERON (1911), VIERECK (1925, 1926), BRETHERS (1927), UCHIDA (1928), SONAN (1929), BLANCHARD (1947), LÓPEZ CRISTÓBAL (1947), WALLEY (1947), HORSTMANN (1969, 1978, 1985, 1987, 2009), TOWNES (1970), GUPTA & MAHESHWARY (1977), KUSIGEMATI (1981, 1982), GAULD (1984), KASPARYAN & DBAR (1985), GUPTA (1987*a, b*), JERMAN & GAULD (1988), RIEDEL (2018), VAS (2019, 2020, 2021, 2023*a, b, c*, 2024), HAN *et al.* (2022), KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* (2022), GALSWORTHY *et al.* (2023), HARALDSEIDE (2023), and on examination of adequate type materials (at least from photos of scientific quality). The specimens were identified by the author using a Nikon SMZ645 stereoscopic microscope. Label data of type specimens are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary. Photos were taken with a Nikon-D7200 camera, equipped with Nikon AF-S Micro Nikkor 105mm objective and DCR-150 Raynox Macro Conversion lens, managed by Helicon Remote, stacked by Helicon Focus.

TAXONOMY

Breviterebra laticlypeata Kusigemati, 1982

Breviterebra laticlypeata Kusigemati, 1982. Original description: KUSIGEMATI (1982: 623); holotype: [Japan:] Muine-yama, Sapporo, Hokkaido; Hokkaido University, Sapporo.

Breviterebra apicocrinis Han, van Achterberg et Chen, 2022, **syn. nov.** Original description: HAN *et al.* (2022: 529); holotype: [China:] Sichuan, Luhuo Zhuweixiang; Zhejiang University, Hangzhou.

Remarks – HAN *et al.* (2022) distinguished *Breviterebra apicocrinis* (described from China) from *Breviterebra laticlypeata* (described from Japan and subsequently reported from the Russian Far East, North Korea, and Germany) primarily by the surface structure of metapleuron, stating that it is

“rugulose between punctures” in *Breviterebra laticlypeata*, but “smooth between punctures” in *Breviterebra apicocrinis*. However, while it is indeed “rugulose” (more precisely rugose, since the rugae are large and prominent) in the examined holotype of *Breviterebra laticlypeata*, it is not smooth but rather rugose in *Breviterebra apicocrinis*, as it is evident from additional photos of the holotype provided by Y.-Y. Han. This character is not clear in illustrations accompanying the original description (HAN *et al.* 2022). The respective holotypes of the two species do not differ in this character. Additional diagnostic characters of the two species proposed by HAN *et al.* (2022) are either invalid (such as the posterior corner of pronotum, which is in fact dark in both species), or insignificant and subject of notable intraspecific variability (such as the colouration of the apices of fore and middle coxae, or very small differences in the ratios of ocular-ocellar distance and ocellus diameter), or have little if any taxonomical value in Campopleginae (such as minor differences in the density of fine pilosity on the metasomal tergites). As for the latter trait, it is also worth noting that the metasomal pilosity of the holotype and additional North Korean material of *Breviterebra laticlypeata*, both examined in course of the present study, is about evenly distributed, and no significant difference between the basal and apical tergites can be observed in respect of its density (see also VAS (2023c)). HAN *et al.* (2022) likely based their comparison on the partly inaccurate original description of *Breviterebra laticlypeata* (KUSIGEMATI 1982) rather than an examination of the holotype. In non-type specimens examined in course of the present study (five females from North Korea) the colouration of the hind femur exhibited various shades from chestnut-brown to orange-brown (see also VAS (2023c)), indicating that this trait is not only insufficient in itself but inadequate for species level differentiation. For the above, *Breviterebra apicocrinis* is hereby downgraded to a junior subjective synonym of *Breviterebra laticlypeata*.

The broad Transpalaeartic distribution of *Breviterebra laticlypeata*, with published records from the Eastern Palaeartic part of Japan (KUSIGEMATI 1982), the Russian Far East (KASPARYAN & DBAR 1985), North Korea (VAS 2023c), and most recently from the Western Palaeartic (Germany) (HARALDSEIDE 2023), seems to indicate that records of *Breviterebra apicocrinis* from China (HAN *et al.* 2022) pertain to the Eastern Palaeartic population of *Breviterebra laticlypeata*. This distribution pattern is common in the subfamily Campopleginae (see e.g., VAS (2019, 2020, 2023c), present study).

***Casinaria molnari* sp. nov.**

(Figs 1–2)

Type material – Holotype: female, “Brasilia, Manaus [= Brazil, Amazonas State, Manaus], 1930.VII.25. [leg. Gábor] Molnár”; card-mounted, id. HNHNH-HYM 155388, deposited in the HNHNH.

Figs 1–2. *Casinaria molnari* sp. nov., 1 = habitus, holotype, 2 = propodeum, surface sculpture not indicated (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Diagnosis – The new species is readily distinguished from all known congeners by the following combination of character states: antenna with a conspicuous, contrasting, long whitish band on flagellomeres 3–12; head lenticular; occipital carina reaching hypostomal carina at base of mandible; face narrow; mesopleuron granulate, impunctate, with strong wrinkles around the granulate, matt speculum; propodeum moderately elongate, lateromedian and lateral longitudinal carinae anterior to costulae strong, posterior to costulae weaker but discernible; anterior transverse carina strong; area superomedia predominantly granulate, hexagonal, 1.5× as long as wide, its lateral sides convergent posterior to costulae, posteriorly opened; second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) at middle of areolet; nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) not intercepted; tegula pale yellow; metasoma extensively reddish brown; fore and middle coxae pale yellow, hind coxa black, apically narrowly yellowish; all trochanters and trochantelli pale yellow; hind femur orange-brown, basally and apically slightly darkened; hind tibia orange-brown, basally with a pale yellowish spot, subbasally and apically brownish.

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length 4 mm, fore wing length 3 mm.

Head: Antenna with 27 flagellomeres, first flagellomere $4\times$ as long as its apical width, preapical flagellomeres quadrate. Head lenticular, transverse, matt, with short, dense hairs. Ocular-ocellar distance $0.7\times$ as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits moderately indented, slightly convergent ventrad. Gena finely coriaceous, very short, strongly narrowed behind eye. Occipital carina complete, moderately bent out ventrally, reaching hypostomal carina at base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons finely granulate with weak, indistinct wrinkles, impressed above toruli, median longitudinal carina absent. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, granulate with weak, indistinct rugulosity; face narrow, minimal width of face ca. $0.45\times$ as long as eye length in frontal view; clypeus small, its apical margin weakly convex, sharp. Malar space $0.5\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible short, wide, lower margin with wide flange from base towards teeth, flange gradually, obliquely narrowed at teeth, upper mandibular tooth slightly longer than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma granulate, matt, at most with weak, indistinct traces of punctures, and with dense, short hairs. Ventral half of pronotum almost smooth with strong, diagonal wrinkles; epomia distinct. Mesoscutum strongly convex in profile, about as long as wide, notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove deep and wide. Scutellum convex in profile, medially not impressed, lateral carinae developed only at the extreme base. Mesopleuron granulate, virtually impunctate, with strong transverse and diagonal wrinkles around speculum; speculum granulate, matt; mesopleural suture impressed. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it at about its middle height, transversal part (i.e., part at level of sternaulus running through epicnemium to ventral edge of pronotum) not developed, ventral part (behind fore coxae) complete, slightly elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated, medially not excised. Metanotum ca. $0.5\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron granulate, impunctate; juxtacoxal carina not developed; submetapleural carina complete, strong, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, oval, separated from pleural carina by slightly more than its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum long, its apex reaching basal third of length of hind coxa in dorsal view, rugose on granulate background, rugosity stronger in posterior half than in anterior half. Propodeal carinae relatively well developed: lateromedian and lateral longitudinal carinae anterior to costulae strong, posterior to costulae significantly weaker but discernible; anterior transverse carina, including costulae, strong; posterior transverse carina medially absent, laterally discernible. Area basalis trapezoid, slightly longer than its anterior width. Area superomedia predominantly granulate, transversely rugose at its apex, hexagonal, $1.5\times$ as long as wide, its lateral carinae convergent behind costulae, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris

confluent with area superomedia, their junction discernible, transversely rugose, medially weakly, widely impressed. Fore wing with short-stalked, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) at about middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* slightly bent towards wing margin; nervulus (*cu-a*) interstitial, strongly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) reclivous, not broken, not intercepted by discoidella (distal abscissa of *Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate. Hind femur 5.5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.65× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small and short, as long as arolium, basal pectines indistinct.

Metasoma: Metasoma moderately compressed, finely granulate to shagreened with dense, short hairs. First tergite long and slender, ca. 4.5× as long as its posterior width, 1.3× as long as second tergite, 0.8× as long as hind femur, without glymma; dorsomedian carina of first tergite absent; postpetiolus moderately bulging, its lateral sides curved in dorsal view. Suture separating first tergite from first sternite situated strongly above mid-height at basal third of first metasomal segment. Second tergite slender, 1.7× as long as its posterior width; thyridium elongate oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite ca. 0.5× as long as its length, connected to basal margin of tergite by a weak, superficial groove. Posterior margins of apical tergites medially slightly and widely concave. Ovipositor sheath about as long as apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor straight.

Colour: Scapus and pedicellus pale yellow with narrow, blackish stripes on outer sides; flagellum blackish with a conspicuous, contrasting, long whitish band on inner sides of flagellomeres 3–12. Head black, except palpi and mandible yellow, and mandibular teeth reddish brown. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma: first tergite and sternite black; second tergite blackish with an orange band on its posterior third; third tergite blackish, posteriorly suffused with reddish brown; following tergites reddish brown, dorsally more or less darkened. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli pale yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi orange, apical tarsomeres darkened. Hind leg: coxa black, apically narrowly yellowish; trochanter and trochantellus pale yellow; femur orange-brown, basally and apically slightly darkened; tibia orange-brown, basally with a distinct, pale yellowish spot, subbasally and apically brownish; tarsus brownish, except extreme base of first tarsomere with a narrow, pale ring.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – Brazil.

Etymology – The new species is dedicated to the memory of Gábor Molnár (1908–1980), Hungarian traveller, hunter, collector and writer, who collected the holotype during his expedition to Brazil; the specific epithet is a proper noun in the genitive case.

Remarks on identification – The only other described *Casinaria* species that possesses a contrasting, whitish band on the flagellum of the female is *Casinaria affinis* Tschek, 1871, distributed in Europe. The white band in this species, however, is distinctly shorter than in the new species, starting from flagellomeres 9–10, and ending on 12–15 (RIEDEL 2018). *Casinaria affinis* is otherwise distinctly different from the new species and they are unlikely to be confused; the contrasting, long whitish band of the new species and the other character states given the Diagnosis allow an unambiguous identification. The presence of a conspicuous whitish band on the flagellum is quite rare in Campopleginae, but is known to occur in females of a few species of the genera *Venturia* Schrottky, 1902, *Cymodusa* Holmgren, 1859, *Callidora* Förster, 1869, *Hyposoter*, and *Casinaria* (TOWNES 1970, GUPTA & MAHESHWARY 1977, DBAR 1984, 1985, RIEDEL 2018, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2022, VAS 2023a). As males in these species usually do not have this trait, it is assumed that it is also missing in the yet unknown male of the new species.

Hyposoter bombycivorus (Cameron, 1911)

Limnerium bombycivorum Cameron, 1911. Original description: CAMERON (1911: 335); holotype: [Australia:] Tasmania; Natural History Museum, London

Hyposoter bombycivorus: TOWNES *et al.* (1961: 240) (new combination).

Eriborus biroi Vas, 2023, **syn. nov.** Original description: VAS (2023a: 78); holotype: Australia, N. S. Wales, Mt. Victoria; HHNM.

Remarks – In the time of the description of *Eriborus biroi* (VAS 2023a), I was unaware that the diagnostic characters widely used for distinguishing *Hyposoter* and *Eriborus* are apparently reliable for Holarctic species, but fail for the Australasian and Oriental materials. In *Eriborus* the hind tarsus is provided with a midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs, appearing as a darker, somewhat scaly line, which is clearly discernible with experience; it is, however, always lacking in *Hyposoter* species (TOWNES 1970). This trait was similarly used by KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* (2022) to differentiate European species of *Eriborus* and *Hyposoter*, despite their caveat that it is subtle and requires experience to discern. The most recent comprehensive work on European *Hyposoter* (GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023) did not mention this trait for any European species of this genus. Given the presence of a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs on its hind tarsus, the specimen later designated as holotype of *Eriborus biroi* was readily sorted into *Eriborus* in 2023, recognised as different from other described species of this genus, and described as new.

However, VAS (2024) discovered that *Hyposoter* species from the Oriental Region might possess a quite distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short

hairs on the hind tarsus, very much like that of *Eriborus*, as it was documented and discussed for the Bornean species *Hyposoter ara* Vas, 2024 by VAS (2024). Hence, the presence or absence of this character state is now considered as less diagnostically reliable. Other supporting characters given by TOWNES (1970) are also of insufficient diagnostic value: in many *Eriborus* species the ovipositor is as short as in *Hyposoter* (in the latter always short by the generic definition); *Eriborus* species always lack an areolet of the fore wing (by the generic definition) while *Hyposoter* species usually have one (it is almost always present in species known from Europe except two (GALSWORTHY *et al.* (2023), while it is frequently lacking in Australasian and Oriental species (SONAN 1929, VAS 2023a)); the mesopleuron (including speculum) is usually matt, granulate in *Hyposoter*, while in *Eriborus* at least the speculum is often more or less smooth and polished. Therefore, specimens with a combination of having a more or less distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs on hind tarsus, a short ovipositor, and a lack of areolet, can be easily misidentified; in such species, the morphology of the clypeus and mandibles remains the most reliable character to distinguish *Eriborus* from *Hyposoter*. In *Eriborus*, the clypeus is weakly convex in profile, its margin is not impressed, usually blunt, it is evenly, weakly convex, the mandibles are often relatively long with a narrower lower carina, while in *Hyposoter* the clypeus is smaller, more convex in profile, its apical margin is convex, more or less impressed and sharp, and the mandibles are always relatively short with a wide lower carina or flange (TOWNES 1970). While the above differences of the clypeus and mandibles still seem reliable, they require considerable experience and examination of comparative materials to avoid misidentifications.

To address these uncertainties, the Oriental and Australasian *Eriborus* and *Hyposoter* materials in the HNHM were re-examined. It was concluded that the holotype of *Eriborus biroi*, while having a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs on hind tarsus and lacking an areolet (both indicating a placement into *Eriborus*!) should rather be classified as a *Hyposoter* based on the morphology of the clypeus and mandibles. A comparison of the type specimens revealed that *Eriborus biroi* (described from Australia, New South Wales) and *Hyposoter bombycivorus* (described as *Limnerium bombycivorum* from Australia, Tasmania) are conspecific, thus *Eriborus biroi* is a junior subjective synonym of *Limnerium bombycivorum*. Although the holotype of *Limnerium bombycivorum* (deposited in the Natural History Museum, London) is in poor condition, lacking its head and all legs, the remaining parts retain enough morphological details to identify it to species and to establish its conspecificity with *Eriborus biroi*.

It is worth noting that, besides the already mentioned *Hyposoter ara*, *Hyposoter posticae* Sonan, 1929, described from Taiwan (SONAN 1929), also possesses a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs on its hind tarsus, moreover it lacks an areolet and has a short ovipositor, thus it could easily be misidentified as *Eriborus*.

Hyposoter is suspected to be polyphyletic, intermingled with other genera such as *Olesicampe* Förster, 1869 or *Diadegma* Förster, 1869, making generic assignment of several species challenging (GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023, VAS 2023a). This renders the status of *Eriborus* ambiguous, as most of the characters proposed to define the genus have proven inconsistent, at least in the Australasian and Oriental regions (VAS 2023a, 2024, present study); similarly, some of the diagnostic characters proposed for *Hyposoter* might be unreliable as well (TOWNES 1970, GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023, VAS 2024). Phylogenetic studies are needed to resolve the status and relationship of *Hyposoter*, *Eriborus*, and other morphologically similar and potentially related campoplegine genera, in order to propose their unambiguous definitions and stabilise their classification and nomenclature.

Hyposoter jolanae sp. nov.

(Figs 3–4)

Type material – Holotype: female, “Paraguay, S. Bernardino [= Cordillera Department, San Bernardino], [1905–1906], [leg.] Babarczy [= Mrs. Jenő Babarczy, née Jolán Jósa]”; specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155389, deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be distinguished from its congeners by the following character states in combination: clypeus almost flat in profile; mesopleuron granulate, impunctate, speculum mostly smooth, subpolished; propodeum moderately long, convex in profile, posteriorly not produced, on granulate background weakly rugulose in anterior half, distinctly rugose in posterior half; propodeal carinae distinct except median part of posterior transverse carina absent; area basalis triangular; area superomedia pentagonal, 1.3× as long as wide, its lateral carinae weakly convergent behind costulae, posteriorly opened; area petiolaris strongly rugose; areolet subsessile, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distal to middle of areolet; nervulus (*cu-a*) strongly postfurcal; second tergite 1.2× as long as its posterior width; posterior margins of apical tergites straight; ovipositor sheath distinctly longer than apical depth of metasoma, clearly protruding beyond apex of metasoma; scapus and pedicellus blackish; tegula yellowish to brownish; metasoma black, second and third tergites posteriorly suffused with orange-brown, second and following sternites orange-brown with darker patches; wings hyaline, pterostigma pale ochre; fore and middle coxae basally black, apically yellowish, hind coxa black; hind femur dark brown; hind tibia basally and apically widely dark brown, medially pale yellowish.

Description – Female (Figs 3–4). Body length 4 mm, fore wing length 3.5 mm.

Figs 3–4. *Hyposoter jolanae* sp. nov., 3 = habitus, holotype, 4 = propodeum, surface sculpture not indicated (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Head: First flagellomere $4\times$ as long as its apical width. Head transverse, matt, granulate, virtually impunctate except clypeus with a few, weak traces of punctures, and with dense, short hairs. Ocular-ocellar distance as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli $1.2\times$ as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, slightly convergent ventrad. Gena in dorsal view $0.45\times$ as long as eye width, strongly but roundly narrowed behind eyes. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons weakly convex, distinctly impressed above toruli, median longitudinal carina absent. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus small, its apical margin weakly convex, impressed, sharp. Malar

space $0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible short and wide, lower margin of mandible with a quite wide flange from base towards teeth, flange moderately abruptly narrowed before teeth; mandibular teeth subequal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate, virtually impunctate, and with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with weak, transverse wrinkles on lower half; epomia weak. Mesoscutum slightly wider than long, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carinae not developed. Mesopleuron granulate, matt, impunctate; speculum partly very finely granulate but mostly smooth, subpolished. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it below its middle height, ventral part not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated. Metanotum ca. $0.5\times$ as long as scutellum, anteriorly with a pair of deep foveae. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete, distinct; propodeal spiracle circular, almost adjacent to pleural carina, connected to pleural carina by conspicuously wide ridge. Propodeum moderately long, convex in profile, posteriorly not produced, on granulate background weakly rugulose in anterior half, distinctly rugose in posterior half. Propodeal carinae distinct except median part of posterior transverse carina absent. Area basalis triangular, slightly longer than its anterior width. Area superomedia granulate with at most weak rugulosity, pentagonal, $1.3\times$ as long as wide, its lateral carinae weakly convergent behind costulae, posteriorly opened (but may appear weakly closed due to rugae of area petiolaris). Area petiolaris strongly rugose, confluent with area superomedia, their junction distinct. Fore wing with subsessile, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distal to middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by ca. $0.2\times$ its length, moderately inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell weakly acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate. Hind femur $5\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia $0.6\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Hind tarsus without a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally weakly pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma short, moderately compressed, granulate to shagreened, and with moderately dense, short hairs. First tergite slender, $3\times$ as long as its posterior width, $1.25\times$ as long as second tergite; glymma distinct; dorsomedian carina of first tergite indistinct. Second tergite $1.2\times$ as long as its posterior width; thyridium subcircular, its distance from anterior margin of tergite about as long as its length. Third tergite quadrate, following tergites transverse. Posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites straight, not excised. Ovipositor sheath distinctly longer than apical depth of metasoma, conspicuously protruding beyond apex of metasoma.

Colour: Antenna, including scapus and pedicellus, blackish to dark brown. Head black, palpi pale orange, mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula proximally yellowish, distally more or less extensively brown (most probably a variable character, as left tegula of the holotype distinctly darker than right one). Metasoma black, second and third tergites posteriorly suffused with orange-brown, second and following sternites orange-brown with darker patches. Wings hyaline, wing veins brown, pterostigma pale ochre. Fore and middle legs: coxae basally black, apically extensively (fore coxa) or narrowly (middle coxa) yellowish; rest of legs orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa black; trochanter black, apically narrowly yellowish; trochantellus orange; femur dark brown, at extreme base and extreme apex narrowly paler; tibia basally and apically widely dark brown, medially pale yellowish; tibial spurs bicoloured, basally pale yellowish, apically dark brownish; tarsus brown, extreme base of first tarsomere narrowly pale yellowish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – Paraguay.

Etymology – The new species is dedicated to the memory of Mrs. Jenő Babarczy, née Jolán Jósa (1881–1950), Hungarian teacher, writer, and, during the years she spent in South America (1905–1906), a collector for the HNHM; the specific epithet is a proper noun in the genitive case.

Remarks on identification – Due to its relatively long ovipositor sheath conspicuously protruding beyond apex of metasoma, the new species cannot be confused with any known Neotropical species of the genus. *Hyposoter vittatus* Vas, 2025, a species recently described from Argentina (Vas 2025), is superficially similar to the *Hyposoter jolanae* sp. nov., however, it can be easily distinguished from the new species by its short ovipositor sheath (shorter than apical depth of metasoma, not protruding beyond apex of metasoma), its conspicuously convex, almost nose-like clypeus (in profile), its much more extensively reddish metasoma, orange hind femur, and its hind tibia being provided with a distinct, yellowish spot at base. The new species is also somewhat similar to the dark form of *Hyposoter caedator* (Gravenhorst, 1829), a Palearctic species; however, the latter species can be readily separated from the new species by its short ovipositor sheath (shorter than apical depth of metasoma, not protruding beyond apex of metasoma) and orange hind femur.

***Melalophacharops australis* (Kusigemati, 1981), comb. nov.**

Microcharops australis Kusigemati, 1981. Original description: KUSIGEMATI (1981: 127); holotype: [Japan:] Hyakuna, Tamagusuku, Okinawa-ken; Hokkaido University, Sapporo.

Eriborus australis: GUPTA (1987a: 445) (new combination).

Remarks – This species, described from Japan, was originally placed into the genus *Microcharops* (KUSIGEMATI 1981), and later transferred to *Eriborus* (GUPTA 1987). A re-examination of its holotype revealed that it possesses the combination of character states that conflict with both of these placements: apical margin of clypeus is sharp, distinctly impressed (not impressed, more or less blunt in *Eriborus*); the midventral row of the hind tarsus is strongly developed, raised carina-like (less developed in *Eriborus*); glymma is small, weak, barely discernible (usually distinct, stronger in *Eriborus*); the subbasal cell of the hind wing is conspicuously narrow, less than half width of basal cell (not conspicuously narrow, more than half width of basal cell in *Eriborus*); axillus vein of fore wing present (absent in *Microcharops*); scutellum convex in profile, its lateral carinae at most basally discernible (scutellum flat in profile, its lateral carinae fully developed in *Microcharops*). These clearly indicate that this species pertains to the genus *Melalophacharops* (TOWNES 1970, GAULD 1984, GUPTA 1987b, VAS 2023b). Thus, the new combination *Melalophacharops australis* is proposed.

Among the known *Melalophacharops* species, *Melalophacharops australis* is similar to *Melalophacharops nitens* Vas, 2023, described from Taiwan (VAS 2023b); however, it can be readily distinguished from the latter species by the following character states: lateral carinae of area superomedia behind costulae distinctly divergent (subparallel to slightly convergent in *Melalophacharops nitens*); hind tibia basally and apically only slightly infusate (basally and apically extensively dark brown in *Melalophacharops nitens*) (KUSIGEMATI 1981, VAS 2023b).

Melalophacharops tamanukii Uchida, 1928

Melalophacharops tamanukii Uchida, 1928. Original description: UCHIDA (1928: 280); lectotype (TOWNES *et al.* 1965: 305): [Japan:] Hokkaido, Sapporo; Hokkaido University, Sapporo.

Microcharops ussuriensis Kasparyan, 1985, **syn. nov.** Original description: KASPARYAN & DBAR (1985: 45); holotype: [Russia:] хабаровск, хехцир; Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg.

Remarks – The examination of the holotype of *Microcharops ussuriensis* (described from Russia, Khabarovsk Krai) revealed that this species possesses the combination of the following character states, conflicting with its current placement in *Microcharops*: axillus vein of fore wing present (absent in *Microcharops*); scutellum convex in profile, its lateral carinae at most basally discernible (scutellum flat in profile, its lateral carinae fully developed in *Microcharops*). These characters clearly place the species into the genus *Melalophacharops* (GUPTA 1987b). Its propodeal carination, dark hind femur and

dark metasoma unambiguously confirm its conspecificity with *Melalophacharops tamanukii* (described from Japan), the holotype of which has also been re-examined in course of the present study. Accordingly, *Microcharops ussuriensis* is downgraded to a junior subjective synonym of *Melalophacharops tamanukii*.

By removing this species from *Microcharops*, this genus is again considered as endemic to the New World, distributed mostly in the Neotropical Region (TOWNES 1970, GUPTA 1987b).

BIOGEOGRAPHY

Campoplex rufocingulatus Horstmann et Yu, 1999

Material examined – **Hungary:** Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County, Bodrogolaszi, 11–18.VII.2025, leg. B. P. Schlitt, V. Gecseg, M. Bernát & D. Balatoni, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 159682.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. This species has been known from Germany, Poland, and Norway so far (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2019).

Dusona bicoloripes (Ashmead, 1906)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County, Lillafüred, Sártai-lápa, 3.VI.2025, leg. G. Katona, B. Tóth, T. Korompai & Á. Horváth, at light, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 159681.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. This species is widely distributed in the Palearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Enytus apostatus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – **Algeria:** Médéa Province, Ouzera, 30.IV.1990, leg. I. Rozner, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 111492. **North Macedonia:** Polog Region, Mavrovo and Rostuša Municipality, Bistra, Mavrovo, spring brooks above the village, 1285 m, 27.IV.2021, leg. T. Kovács, D. Murányi & P. Olajos, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 158030.

Remarks – First records from Algeria and from North Macedonia. This species is widely distributed in the Palearctic Region, also occurring in the Oriental, Afrotropical and Nearctic Regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hyposoter caedator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – **Bosnia and Herzegovina:** Jablanica, 20–21.VI.1911, leg. unknown, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 158023.

Remarks – First record from Bosnia and Herzegovina. This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hyposoter virginalis (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – **Hungary**: Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County, Komlóska, Szarka-kút, 14–15.VII.2025, leg. B. P. Schlitt, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 159699.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Tranosema latiusculum Thomson, 1887

Material examined – **China**: Beijing, Fragrant Hills Park, 1.VI.1992, leg. L. Papp, one female, id. HNHM-HYM 159646.

Remarks – First record from China. This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016), and is reported here for the first time from the Eastern Palaearctic Region.

*

Acknowledgements – Thanks are due to Gavin Broad (Natural History Museum, London), Yvonnick Gerard and Tim Laebens (Royal Belgian Institute for Natural Sciences, Brussels), Yuan-Yuan Han (Chuzhou University, Chuzhou), Andrey Khalaim (Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg), Yuji Omatsu and Juriya Okayasu (Hokkaido University, Sapporo) for photos of type specimens deposited in their institutions, to Janko A. Kolarov (Plovdiv University, Plovdiv) for the corrections and comments on the manuscript, to Viktória Szóke (HNHM) for drawings and post-image works, and to those who collected/donated the mentioned specimens for the Hymenoptera Collection of the HNHM.

REFERENCES

- BLANCHARD E. E. 1947: Nuevos géneros y especies de insectos parásitos (Hymenoptera & Diptera) del Uruguay. – *Comunicaciones Zoológicas del Museo de Historia Natural de Montevideo* 2(42): 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.21902>
- BRETHES J. 1927: Hyménoptères sud-américains du Deutsches Entomologisches Institut: Terebrantia. (Schluss). – *Entomologische Mitteilungen* 16: 319–335.

- CAMERON P. 1911: On a collection of parasitic Hymenoptera (chiefly bred) made by Mr. W.W. Froggatt, F.L.S., in New South Wales, with descriptions of new genera and species. Part i. – *Proceedings of the Linnean Society of New South Wales* **36**: 333–346.
- CRESSON E. T. 1865: On the Hymenoptera of Cuba. – *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Philadelphia* **4**: 1–200.
- CRESSON E. T. 1872: Hymenoptera Texana. – *Transactions of the American Entomological Society* **4**: 153–292. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25076272>
- CRESSON E. T. 1874: Descriptions of Mexican Ichneumonidae. – *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia* **1873**: 374–413.
- DBAR R. S. 1984: (Review of the Palearctic species of the genus *Cymodusa* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). I.) – *Entomologicheskoye Obozreniye* **63**: 802–812.
- DBAR R. S. 1985: (Revision of the Palearctic species of *Cymodusa* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). II.) – *Entomologicheskoye Obozreniye* **64**: 588–600.
- GALSWORTHY A., SHAW M. R. & HARALDSEIDE H. 2023: A key to European species of Hyposoter Förster, 1869 (Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae) with descriptions of 18 new species, and notes on all included species. – *Zootaxa* **5290**(1): 1–73. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5290.1.1>
- GAULD I. D. 1984: *An introduction to the Ichneumonidae of Australia*. – British Museum (Natural History), London, 413 pp.
- GAULD I. D. 1991: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 1. Introduction, keys to subfamilies, and keys to the species of the lower Pimpliform subfamilies Rhyssinae, Poemeniinae, Acaenitinae and Cyloceriinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **47**: 1–589.
- GAULD I. D., WAHL D., BRADSHAW K., HANSON P. & WARD S. 1997: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 2. Introduction and keys to species of the smaller subfamilies, Anomaloninae, Ctenopelmatinae, Diplazontinae, Lycorininae, Phrudinae, Tryphoninae (excluding Netelia) and Xoridinae, with an appendix on the Rhyssinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **57**: 1–485.
- GUPTA V. K. & MAHESHWARY S. 1977: Ichneumonologia Orientalis. Part IV. The tribe Porizontini (=Campoplegini) (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Oriental Insects Monographs* **5**: 1–267.
- GUPTA V. K. 1987a: The Ichneumonidae of the Indo-Australian area (Hymenoptera). – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **41**(1): 1–597.
- GUPTA V. K. 1987b: A revision of the genus *Microcharops* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) – *Contributions to the American Entomological Institute* **23**(2): 1–42.
- HAN Y.-Y., VAN ACHTERBERG C. & CHEN X.-X. 2022: Review of the genera *Breviterebra* Kusigemati, *Charops* Holmgren and *Scenocharops* Uchida (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Campopleginae) from China, with description of three new species. – *Zootaxa* **5133**(4): 527–542. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5133.4.4>
- HARALDSEIDE H. 2023: Six campoplegines new to Germany, including first record of *Breviterebra* Kusigemati, 1982 (Campopleginae, Ichneumonidae, Hymenoptera) from the Western Palearctic. – *Norwegian Journal of Entomology* **70**: 6–9.
- HARRIS R. A. 1979: A glossary of surface sculpturing. – *Occasional Papers in Entomology* **28**: 1–31.
- HORSTMANN K. 1969: Typenrevision der europäischen Arten der Gattung *Diadegma* Förster (syn. *Angitia* Holmgren). – *Beiträge zur Entomologie* **19**: 413–472.

- HORSTMANN K. 1978: Bemerkungen zur Systematik einiger Gattungen der Campopleginae. – *Mitteilungen Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft* **67**: 65–83.
- HORSTMANN K. 1985: Revision der mit difformis (Gmelin, 1790) verwandten westpaläarktischen Arten der Gattung Campoplex Gravenhorst, 1829 (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Entomofauna* **6**(12): 129–163.
- HORSTMANN K. 1987: Die europäischen Arten der Gattung Echthronomas Förster und Eriborus Förster (Hym., Ichneumonidae). – *Nachrichtenblatt der Bayerischen Entomologen* **36**: 57–67.
- HORSTMANN K. 2009: Revision of the Western Palearctic species of *Dusona* Cameron (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Campopleginae). – *Spixiana* **32**(2): 45–110.
- JERMAN E. J. & GAULD I. 1988: *Casinarina*, a paraphyletic ichneumonid genus (Hymenoptera), and a revision of the Australian species. – *Journal of Natural History* **22**(3): 589–609.
- KASPARYAN D. R. & DBAR R. S. 1985: (On the taxonomy of Ichneumonids of the subfamily Campopleginae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) in the Far East of the USSR.) – *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute, Leningrad* **132**: 40–53.
- KLOPFSTEIN S., BROAD G. R., URFER K., VÅRDAL H. & HARALDSEIDE H. 2022: An interactive key to the European genera of Campopleginae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) and 20 new species for Sweden. – *Entomologisk Tidskrift* **143**(3): 121–156.
- KUSIGEMATI K. 1981: A new species of the genus *Microcharops* Roman from Japan (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Memoirs of the Faculty of Agriculture, Kagoshima University* **17**: 127–130.
- KUSIGEMATI K. 1982: A new Porizontine genus *Breviterebra* from Japan (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Kontyu* **50**(4): 621–625.
- LÓPEZ CRISTÓBAL U. 1947: Dos nuevos Himenópteros útiles. – *Revista de Investigaciones Agrícolas* **1**: 279–282.
- RIEDEL M. 2018: Revision of the Western Palearctic species of the genus *Casinarina* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Campopleginae). – *Linzer biologische Beiträge* **50**(1): 687–716.
- RIEDEL M. 2019: Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) new for the fauna of Norway, Part 8. – *Norwegian Journal of Entomology* **66**: 65–70.
- SAY T. 1835: Descriptions of new North American Hymenoptera, and observations on some already described. – *Boston Journal of Natural History* **1**(3): 210–305.
- SCHROTTKY C. 1902: Neue argentinische Hymenoptera. – *Anales del Museo Nacional de Buenos Aires* **8**: 91–117.
- SONAN J. 1929: A few host-known Ichneumonidae found in Formosa (Hym.). – *Transactions of the Natural History Society of Formosa* **19**: 415–425.
- TOSQUINET J. 1903: Ichneumonides nouveaux. – *Mémoires de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* **10**: 1–403.
- TOWNES H. 1969: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 1. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **11**: 1–300.
- TOWNES H. 1970: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 3. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **13**: 1–307.
- TOWNES H., MOMOI S. & TOWNES M. 1965: A catalogue and reclassification of the Eastern Palearctic Ichneumonidae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **5**: 1–661.

- TOWNES H., TOWNES M. & GUPTA V. K. 1961: A catalogue and reclassification of the Indo-Australian Ichneumonidae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **1**: 1–522.
- TSCHERK C. 1871: Ichneumonologische Fragmente. – *Verhandlungen der Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien* **21**: 37–68.
- UCHIDA T. 1928: Zweiter Beitrag zur Ichneumoniden-Fauna Japans. – *Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University* **21**: 177–297.
- VAS Z. 2019: New species and new records of Campopleginae from the Palaearctic region (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **80**: 247–271.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2019.80.247>
- VAS Z. 2020: Contributions to the taxonomy and biogeography of Nemeritis Holmgren (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae). – *Zootaxa* **4758**(3): 486–500.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4758.3.4>
- VAS Z. 2021: New species and records of Afrotropical Campopleginae III. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **82**: 23–42.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2021.82.23>
- VAS Z. 2023a: Still from Bíró's cornucopia: new species and new records of Campopleginae from Australia (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **84**: 63–97.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2023.84.63>
- VAS Z. 2023b: New species and new records of ichneumon wasps, with descriptions of two new species of Melalophacharops Uchida, 1928 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **84**: 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2023.84.47>
- VAS Z. 2023c: “Revisiting” North Korea: new species and new records of Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Annales Musei historico-naturalis hungarici* **115**: 215–235. <https://doi.org/10.53019/AnnlsMusHistNatHung.2023.115.215>
- VAS Z. 2024: New species and new records of Oriental Campopleginae and Nesomesochorinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **85**: 61–79.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2024.85.61>
- VAS Z. 2025: The zoological results of Gy. Topál's collectings in South Argentina. 28. Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae: Hyposoter Förster, 1869 and Campoletis Förster, 1869 (Hymenoptera). – *Annales Musei historico-naturalis hungarici* **117**: 47–64.
<https://doi.org/10.53019/AnnlsMusHistNatHung.2025.117.47>
- VIERECK H. L. 1925: A preliminary revision of the Campopleginae in the Canadian National Collection, Ottawa. – *Canadian Entomologist* **57**: 176–181, 198–204, 223–228, 296–303.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent57296-12>
- VIERECK H. L. 1926: A preliminary revision of some Charopsinae, a sub-family of Ichneumonoidea or ichneumon flies. – *Proceedings and Transactions of the Royal Society of Canada* **20**: 173–186.
- WALLEY G. S. 1947: The genus Casinaria Holmgren in America north of Mexico (Hymen., Ichneumonidae). – *Scientific Agriculture* **27**: 364–395.
- YU D. S. & HORSTMANN K. 1997: *A catalogue of world Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera)*. – The American Entomological Institute, Gainesville, 1558 pp.
- YU D. S., VAN ACHTERBERG C. & HORSTMANN K. 2016: *Taxapad 2016, Ichneumonoidea 2015*. – Database on flash-drive. www.taxapad.com, Nepean, Ontario, Canada.